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IMPROVING EDUCATIONAL PROCESS BY PROVIDING CROSS- SUBJECT INTEGRATION

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Annotation: The paper provides a description of the essence and content of the concepts of integration, theoretical issues, types of integration of education, the content of pedagogical activity, ensuring the integration of education, the requirements and rules of integrative principles, the process of improving the content of education, improving curricula.

Key words: educational process, integration, interdisciplinary integration, content improvement, principles, curricula, didactic functions, efficiency.

Scientists from foreign countries and the Republic of Uzbekistan highlighted the methodological system for training future engineers as highly qualified specialists by ensuring the integration of general professional and special disciplines in the field of technical higher education, the essence, theory and practice, the main didactic functions and principles of interdisciplinary integration. However, we consider it necessary to regard and interpret interdisciplinary integration not only as educational and methodological support, but more broadly as an interconnected activity of faculty and students, a system of all elements of the educational process.

Most of the top-priority areas in the social sphere represent a complex of research into the forms of integration of education at foreign universities with science and

industry. Scientific research on integration in technical higher education is carried out by leading research centers and higher educational institutions of the world, including Massachusetts Institute of Technology (USA), Stanford University (USA), University of Texas (USA), Manchester Metropolitan University (USA), London University (UK), Oxford University (UK), Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (Germany), Zhejiang University (China), Lomonosov Moscow State University (Russia), The Massachusetts Institute of Technology (USA), justified the mechanisms for improving the quality of training based on the integration of disciplines in higher education as a result of research related to the development of higher education based on an integrative approach to it, conducted around the world. Humber Institute of Technology (USA), Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (Malaysia), University of Tokyo (Japan) created a system for assessing the development of professional skills of future specialists using modern didactic educational tools based on integrative technologies for the mutual exchange of information between educational institutions and production enterprises. The National Institute of Technical Teachers Training and Research (India), as well as the Bukhara Engineering-Technology Institute (Uzbekistan) are developing the principles of integrative design of the educational process, quantitative and qualitative approaches to the algorithm of teacher and student activity.

The creation of conditions that allow the training of specialists with professional skills and high qualifications, the organization of the educational process according to a methodology based on the integration of academic disciplines, and the scientific justification for its formation and development in accordance with socio-economic conditions, as well as the need to develop its methodological system determine the relevance of the present study. The practical significance of the implementation of training on the basis of ensuring the integration of the content of special disciplines and general professional disciplines in the areas of study of light industry in higher education is determined by the appropriate productive use of improved educational and

methodological support. Based on the foregoing, we have identified the possibilities of using various types of integration to achieve the effectiveness of the educational process (see: Figure 1).

Figure 1. The use of various types of integration in the educational process

The integration of education is understood not only as an interdisciplinary connection of knowledge, but also as an integration of educational technologies, methods and forms. In our opinion, an integrative approach to education means not a one-sided, but a multifaceted, multilateral approach.

The content of pedagogical activity based on ensuring the integration of education is revealed by the functions, requirements and rules of integrative principles. Interdisciplinary integration demonstrates its practical results in conjunction with such didactic principles as inseparability, consistency, communication and innovation.

Therefore, in the process of integrative improvement of the content of education, the integration of the education system is an important principle for the modernization of education, which, on the one hand, is the provision of inseparability, the sequence of various stages of education, on the other hand, the principle of ensuring the continuity of education, designed for multidimensional actions in the educational process. In the methodological essence of the problem of interdisciplinary connections, the educational process is organized in such a way that the use of knowledge, skills and abilities that have been mastered in the study of one discipline has its place in the study of other disciplines [1].

In technical higher education, there are opportunities to ensure the integration of disciplines, this process is provided in conjunction with such principles of organizing an integrative process as inseparability, consistency, communication and innovation. On their basis, the programs of disciplines are improved, educational literature of a new content, educational and methodological complexes are created. As a result, integration between academic disciplines is ensured, integration in the content of a separate discipline, integrity, quality and creativity appear in the content of education. From the analysis of ensuring interdisciplinary integration in education, it can be seen that there is a need to develop and research teaching methods that provide integration between general professional and special disciplines in the field of light industry in technical higher educational institutions.

Figure 2. Results of the application of integrative relations between teachers and students

An integrative approach to the relationship between academic disciplines is based on didactic perception: the teacher introduces the student to the goals and objectives of the topic being studied, its relationship with other topics and the effectiveness of communicative didactic tools (see: Figure 2).

We have determined the factors influencing the bases of integration which are: objective regularities in the development of sciences; determination of the content of education, taking into account the development of science and technology; state educational standards and qualification requirements; tasks of education, synthesis of knowledge; the unity of the process and content of education; determination of the interaction of the curriculum; material base; pedagogical and information technologies.

Studies show that the integrative system of higher education has a significant impact on the cognitive activity of students. The complexity and dynamism of the education system based on integration creates opportunities for the realization of individual interests, inclinations and professional competencies of students, taking into account the individuality and differentiation of education.

Substantial improvement of curricula and programs of disciplines makes it convenient to effectively organize the educational process, expedient and correct use of the volume of hours allocated for disciplines, control and monitoring of the implementation of general workloads. Based on the integrative principles of education, interdisciplinary integration has been achieved through the improvement of curricula and programs, analysis of the relationship between general professional and special disciplines.

Based on the above, educational materials based on the integration between academic disciplines have been developed and implemented directly into the educational process. Therefore, the improvement of curricula and programs used in higher educational institutions, based on the requirements and proposals of employers,

the educational and technical capabilities of the educational institution and the conditions of the labor market in a given territory, will lead to an increase in the quality of vocational education [2].

Goals, objectives, opportunities for an integrative educational environment are formed depending on the level of students' preparation and pedagogical conditions. It is known from scientific research that the problem of interdisciplinary and interdisciplinary communication in the content of curricula and programs is solved on the basis of ensuring integration in the content of each academic discipline, as well as integrity, quality and creativity.

In our opinion, the integration of academic disciplines will lead to the effective use of time allocated for classes, increased motivation among students, perception of knowledge by eliminating duplication of content in various academic disciplines. Systematic and organic consolidation of knowledge and skills on a new topic forms the ability of proficient use of acquired knowledge among students.

Consequently, the integrative reform of the education system based on a holistic perception of the surrounding world by students consists in the integration of educational material, the establishment and generalization of interdisciplinary links and dependencies, and serves as the leading form of organizing the content of education.

As a result of research, it has been determined that integrative learning provides the following:

- ✓ student training, the transformation of his knowledge into skills affect his qualifications and professional practice;
- ✓ leads to the emergence of integration between processes, phenomena, ideas and concepts studied in the content of the modules;
- ✓ knowledge obtained, applied, generalized through integration, improves students' understanding, facilitates and intensifies the perception of information;
- ✓ the unity of education and upbringing is ensured;

- ✓ the principles of ensuring the integration of general professional and special disciplines are being introduced into the educational process;
- ✓ the connection between the content of education, educational materials and basic concepts is provided.

In the methodological essence of the problem of interdisciplinary relations, the learning process is organized in such a way that its place is taken by the use of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the study of one subject for the study of other subjects. Consequently, the main problem of interdisciplinary relations is the classification that determines the main currents of their possible relations, that is, the generalization of the content of the materials taught, scientific methods [2].

Therefore, integrative education can be implemented in the following way: showing the mutual influence between the content, forms of education, the relationship between individual parts and stages, constant reliance on existing knowledge, skills and experience in the assimilation of new educational material, ensuring the integration of special disciplines in the field of light industry at the undergraduate level, the choice of forms and methods of independent work of students at each stage of training, the gradual complication, deepening generalization and systematization of the volume and level of independent work of students.

For the purpose of qualitative organization of classes through the implementation in practice of improved programs for each academic discipline, while ensuring the integration and inseparability of the humanities and natural sciences, general professional and special disciplines, as well as ensuring the integration of special disciplines in the educational direction of the bachelor's degree in higher education, it is possible to achieve a further increase in efficiency of education by revising the content of the programs and modules of the disciplines of each block and the time allocated for their teaching, as a result of organizing education based on integrative and competence-based approaches [3].

To compare the frequencies of one series of results obtained in the experiment with the frequencies of their other series, to determine the differences between the theoretical frequencies and the experimental series of frequencies, the goodness of fit criterion χ^2 (“Chi squared”), proposed by the English statistician K. Pearson, was used. The reliability of the results was determined by comparing the values of $T_{\text{control}} < T_{\text{exper}}$, that is, in the table, the value of χ^2 was $T_{\text{control}} = 13.28\%$ and $T_{\text{exper}} = 27.5\%$. This indicates that the significance of the difference between them is $P < 0.01$.

From the above analysis, it can be seen that the use of the developed methodology for ensuring the integration of general professional and special disciplines in higher education led to the achievement of the following efficiency in the educational process: in the experimental group, the level of assimilation for the grade "excellent" increased by 9.43%, for the grade "good" - by 10.69%, the number of those who received the rating "satisfactory" decreased by 8.81%, the rating "unsatisfactory" - by 11.32%. Consequently, in the experimental groups, compared with the control groups, the number of students who received "excellent" and "good" grades increased (see: Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3. The results of the evaluation of students of the experimental group (n=159) in a special discipline

Figure 4. The results of the assessment of students in the control group (n₁ = 168) in a special discipline

The levels of students' preparation for professional activities on the basis of interdisciplinary integrated learning are determined for each criterion indicator, the results of pedagogical experimental work are processed by methods of mathematical statistics. According to the results of the research, in terms of preparing students for professional activities, there is a positive trend of 14.22%. This proves the effectiveness of the organizational and structural model developed by us and the developed methodology (see: table 1).

Table 1

The level of general assimilation of students of the experimental and control groups in a special discipline

Groups	Number of	The results of assessing the level of knowledge of students								Overall average score	Average result
		"unsatisfactory"		"satisfactory"		"Good"		"Great"			
		number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	%	
Experimental group	159	10	6,29	52	32,7	59	37,1	38	23,9	T _{exp} = 27,5	14,22
Control group	168	16	9,52	70	41,7	48	28,8	34	20,2	T _{cont} = 13,28	

Thus, it can be said that through the organization of the educational process on the basis of improving the curricula of the bachelor's degree of higher educational institutions, teaching methods based on the programs of disciplines in which the integration of general professional and special disciplines is ensured, it is possible to achieve high efficiency in education, educate process engineers, with deep knowledge and practical skills.

On the basis of interdisciplinary integration training of future process engineers, conducted integrative training was aimed at developing the necessary professional competencies such as production, design, and construction. It is shown and substantiated that the organization of training using the discipline integration methodology is the presentation of new topics integrated with existing knowledge and skills from other related disciplines. The principles of ensuring the integration of disciplines in the educational process in the field of higher education are systematized, the possibilities of meaningful convergence of general educational and specialized disciplines are disclosed.

We believe that through these scientific studies we have partially solved the problem of ensuring the integration of general professional and special disciplines on the example of the educational direction of light industry. The problem of ensuring the integration of disciplines is an urgent problem of education, therefore we believe that it should be continued to study it, to carry out a lot of research, as well as scientific, methodological, conceptual reforms.

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